

Inverse Design of Phononic Crystals: a Benchmarking of Traditional and Sequence-Based Machine Learning Methods

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Abstract—Phononic crystals feature periodic arrangements of acoustic scatterers that create bandgaps—frequency ranges and directions where wave propagation is forbidden, enabling applications in vibration isolation, acoustic filtering, and waveguiding. To predict the bandgaps, finite element modeling and plane-wave expansion are often used. However, they often requiring long computational time per single configuration. Recent machine learning methods have shown promise in accelerating bandgap prediction when trained over an extended database of phononic crystals configurations. Nonetheless, most of the explored methods often assume fixed-size outputs and overlook multi-bandgap configurations. This work presents a framework overcoming such limitations via Sequence-based models that predict the full bandgap spectrum of a configuration without assumptions on the number or existence of gaps. A comparison of their capabilities with respect to standard machine learning approaches - Random Forest and XGBoost - is given, as well as an example of their inverse design capability. This framework represents a step forward in machine learning-driven design, enabling rapid exploration of bandgap-rich configurations for next-generation acoustic devices.

Keywords—Phononic crystals, bandgaps prediction, machine learning, sequence-based models, inverse design, ultrasounds

I. INTRODUCTION

Phononic crystals (PnCs) are engineered materials with scatterers embedded in a host medium, producing periodic modulation of mass, density, and elasticity. This periodicity yields bandgaps (BGs)—frequency ranges and directions where acoustic wave propagation is forbidden [1]. The presence, width (BG^W), and central frequency (BG^{fc}) of BGs determine PnCs' functional properties, enabling applications in vibration isolation [2], acoustic filtering [3], and many others.

Designing optimal PnC configurations is challenging since their performance depends on multiple factors — geometry, inclusions arrangement, size, and material properties [4]. Traditional numerical methods (e.g., FEM, plane-wave expansion) for BG prediction are computationally expensive, often requiring hours or days per configuration.

To overcome this, machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) have been widely adopted for efficient BG prediction. For instance, Sadat et al. [5] used random forests to predict BG presence ($R^2 = 0.66$ for BG^{fc} , 0.85 for BG^W); Kumar et al. (2020) applied autoencoders to extract and optimize geometric features [6]; Ibrahim et al. [7] used active learning with Gaussian Process Regression, and Farajollahi et al. achieved near-perfect accuracy ($R^2 \approx 0.997$) with deep neural networks [8]. Inverse design of PnC has been also showed using DL, see for instance [9].

Despite progress, limitations remain. Most models treat BGs prediction as binary classification (“gap” vs. “no-gap”) or focus only on the largest BG. Standard ML approaches also require fixed-size inputs/outputs, making them unsuitable for PnCs with variable numbers of BGs, while often functioning as black boxes with limited physical interpretability.

This research introduces variable-length BG prediction using sequence models (Transformers, LSTM, GRU) [10-12] for two regression tasks, *i.e.* estimating both the BG^W and BG^{fc} of BGs. These architectures predict the full BG spectrum of a given PnC configuration, naturally handling zero, one, or multiple gaps without prior assumptions. A comparison of their capabilities with respect to classical ML models, *i.e.* Random Forest (RF) [13] and XGBoost [14], is shown, as well as an example of a light architecture for the inverse design of PnCs leveraging a surrogate approach [15].

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Database creation

An extended database of 7203 PnCs configurations has been generated using COMSOL Multiphysics 6.3 (FEM, solid mechanics module) by computing wave dispersion diagrams for 2D square-lattice arrangements of circular inclusions within a square host matrix. Figure 1 illustrates the periodic arrangement and corresponding unit cell, along with the simulated mechanical properties, geometrical parameters, and the principal directions in reciprocal space used to solve the eigenvalue problem for dispersion curve computation.

Fig. 1: A sketch of the simulated 2D arrangement of the phononic crystals, showing the specified geometrical parameters and mechanical properties. The spanned directions of the irreducible Brillouin zone are also highlighted.

The following values of geometrical parameters and mechanical properties have been simulated, while the lattice parameter A has been left fixed in value and equal to 2.5 mm:

- radius of the inclusion, r : 0.5, 1.5, and 2.25 mm;
- Young's moduli of host and inclusion, E_{host} and E_{incl} : 1, 3, 10, 30, 100, 300, and 1000 GPa;
- densities of host and inclusion, ρ_{host} and ρ_{incl} : 500, 1000, 2000, 4000, 8000, 16000, and 24000 $kg \cdot m^{-3}$.

It must be noted that such combination of parameters' values yield BGs fall within the sub-MHz regime, a range of interest for both medical ultrasounds and non-destructive evaluation [16]. Furthermore, most Young's modulus-density combinations studied match real materials such as polymers, foams, composite, metals, stiff ceramic, etc. Some pairings, however, like very low modulus with unusually high density, do not exist in nature. These can still be realized with architected mechanical metamaterials, whose engineered microstructures decouple stiffness from density, unlocking behaviors beyond traditional materials [4].

B. Bandgaps identification and categories

A Python script has been used to detect and classify BGs by evaluating the minimum separation between consecutive dispersion curves along the y -axis. A gap was considered valid only when its bandwidth BG^W exceeded 10% of the corresponding central frequency BG^{fc} . This criterion allowed for assigning a binary label, with 1 indicating the presence of a bandgap and 0 its absence.

Furthermore, the identified BGs were then grouped into three categories depending on the BG^W/BG^{fc} ratio γ :

- **Small bandgaps:** $0.1 < \gamma \leq 0.2$
- **Medium bandgaps:** $0.2 < \gamma \leq 0.4$
- **Large bandgaps:** $\gamma > 0.4$

As an illustration of this procedure, Figure 2 reports the dispersion diagram of a representative PnC configuration, where three distinct bandgaps exist.

Fig. 2: example of a dispersion diagram computed via FEM. The employed classification of BGs and their features is also reported.

Figure 3 show the distribution obtained by using the described approach:

Fig. 3: obtained BGs distribution and properties. Text in light-gray indicates the minimum and maximum frequency values found for each of the BGs categories.

It can be noticed that most of the configurations do not lead to the formation of any bandgaps, *i.e.* only 16.7% out of 7203 have at least one BG. This unbalance should be handled with the due care when training the models - an exhaustive discussion on how this has been tackled is out of the scope of the present research and will be detailed in future work.

It is worth stressing that while medium and large BGs are present only once for a given PnC configuration, *i.e.* maximum vector length equal in value to 1, small BGs are often present multiple times, *i.e.* up to 4 for a single configuration, hence the need for sequence models.

C. Employed models

Two groups of models have been used and compared:

Classical regression models:

- Random Forest (RF)
- XGBoost (XGB)

Sequence models

- Long Short-Term Memory networks (LSTM)
- Gated Recurrent Units (GRU)
- Transformer architectures

For a detailed discussion of these techniques, the reader is referred to the relevant literature.

All models have been assessed using standard regression metrics, *i.e.* mean absolute error (MAE), RMSE,

and coefficient of determination (R^2). For sequence models, these metrics were adapted to account for the variable-length nature of the predicted outputs.

A total of 19 features has been used to train the models. These are the results of non-trivial combinations (physically-informed interactions) of the five PnC geometrical and mechanical properties detailed in Sect. II-A, *i.e.* r , E_{host} , E_{incl} , ρ_{host} , ρ_{incl} , *e.g.* acoustic impedance mismatch, density contrast, stiffness contrast, as well as their non-linear interactions.

III. RESULTS

A. Classical models

Table I shows that classical regressors explain only ~ 52 % of the variance for small BG^W , improving to ~ 76 % for medium and to ~ 92 % for large BG^W . The drop in fidelity mirrors both the scarcity of positive samples and the broad dynamic range of BG^W .

TABLE I: PERFORMANCES OF CLASSICAL MODELS - BG^W

BG type	Best model	R^2	MAE (Hz)	RMSE (Hz)
Small	XGBoost	0.521	2642	4125
Medium	Random Forest	0.757	3002	3980
Large	XGBoost	0.924	3589	4847

A similar trend emerges for central frequencies BG^{fc} prediction – BG^{fc} for small BGs remain elusive ($R^2 = 0.428$), whereas that of the large ones are predicted with high certainty ($R^2 = 0.924$).

TABLE II: PERFORMANCES OF CLASSICAL MODELS - BG^{fc}

BG type	Best model	R^2	MAE (Hz)	RMSE (Hz)
Small	XGBoost	0.428	19953	31560
Medium	Random Forest	0.631	12896	17723
Large	XGBoost	0.924	4373	6455

B. Improvements with Sequence models

The use of Sequence models improves performance drastically with respect to the classical ones. The LSTM lifts R^2 from 0.52 to 0.95 for the BG^W of small BGs and yields a 67% MAE improvement, while the Transformer obtained a $R^2 = 0.981$ for BG^W of large BGs.

TABLE III: PERFORMANCES OF SEQUENCE MODELS - BG^{fc}

BG type	R^2	MAE (Hz)	Best model	Seq. R^2	Seq. MAE (Hz)	ΔR^2 (%)
Small	0.521	2642	LSTM	0.951	868	+83
Medium	0.757	3002	Transf	0.921	1175	+22
Large	0.924	3589	Transf	0.981	1208	+6

High improvements are also found for BG^{fc} prediction, especially for the small BGs ones, see Table IV.

TABLE IV: PERFORMANCES OF SEQUENCE MODELS - BG^{fc}

BG type	R^2	MAE (Hz)	Best model	Seq. R^2	Seq. MAE (Hz)	ΔR^2 (%)
Small	0.428	19953	Transf	0.933	5731	+118
Medium	0.631	12896	Transf	0.986	2234	+56
Large	0.924	4373	Transf	0.995	923	+8

C. Inverse Design

A surrogate-model-based parametric optimization system is implemented, leveraging Transformer sequence models previously trained. The system is designed to operate bidirectionally. The core mechanism is based on the use of trained forward models within an optimization loop. For a given target, *e.g.* BG^W or BG^{fc} , the procedure is as follows:

- The nearest successful design is retrieved from the training database, *i.e.* retrieving a set of starting parameters values $\{r, E_{host}, E_{incl}, \rho_{host}, \rho_{incl}\}$;
- Optimization is initialized from this known-feasible design to ensure that the search remains within the viable design space;
- The parameters are iteratively adjusted using gradient-based optimization, *i.e.* Limited-memory Broyden–Fletcher–Goldfarb–Shanno with Box constraints (L-BFGS-B). At each step:
 - The Transformer models are used to predict BGs properties for the proposed parameters;
 - An objective function is evaluated by computing the error between the predicted and target values;
 - The parameters are subsequently updated to minimize this error;
- Multiple restarts with small perturbations are performed in order to mitigate potential convergence to local minima.

As an example of the results achievable with this framework, a PnC configuration with large BG with $BG^W = 20$ kHz and $BG^{fc} = 52$ kHz has been targeted, *i.e.* a large BG. The inverse design output a reasonable set of $\{r, E_{host}, E_{incl}, \rho_{host}, \rho_{incl}\}$, which when FEM-simulated, yield to $BG^W = 14.7$ kHz and $BG^{fc} = 60.8$ kHz. These errors reflect the fundamental challenge that only a small percentage, *i.e.* 4.3%, of the parameter space produces large BGs.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that sequence-based models — LSTM, GRU, and Transformer — outperform traditional methods like Random Forest and XGBoost in predicting the full spectrum of phononic crystal bandgaps. The proposed framework enables efficient inverse design, allowing rapid exploration of configurations with desired acoustic properties. Future work will extend the approach to 3D and non-square-lattice phononic crystals, incorporate

experimental validation, and explore physics-informed machine learning in detail, to enhance accuracy and interpretability. Dataset imbalance will also be considered in detail and handled carefully, improving robustness across the full parameter space will further support practical design of next-generation acoustic device.

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